

Some Thiocyanato, Cyanato and Selenocyanato Complexes of Copper(II) with Propylene Diamine and Diethylenediamine

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The following complexes of copper(II) with propylenediamine (Pn) and diethylenediamine (DiEn) have been prepared: (CuL_2X_2) ($\text{X}=\text{SCN}^-$, NCO^-) and $[\text{CuL}_2\text{SeCN}]\text{NO}_3$ where L is Pn or DiEn. They have normal magnetic moments and conductivity measurements in pyridine indicate that the selenocyanato complexes are univalent electrolytes and the rest of the complexes are essentially non-electrolytes. Their structures are deduced from i.r. and visible spectra in solution. All the complexes are six co-ordinated with tetragonal symmetry.

CURRENTLY there is a great deal of interest in the study of linkage isomerism of pseudohalides in the co-ordination compounds. The best potential ligands taken for study are SCN^- , SeCN^- and CNO^- . The studies with the most effectively investigated SCN ion in particular, show¹ that various factors like the effect of other ligands including their basicity and steric hindrance; π -bonding and preparative conditions are responsible for the mode of bonding of the ion to the metal. For example, replacement of one of the two S-bonded thiocyanate groups in $\text{CuPn}_2(\text{SCN})_2$ by a weakly co-ordinating group, such as perchlorate or molecule of solvent, causes isomerisation of the remaining thiocyanate group from being S- to N-bonded². Steric factors³ can also alter the mode of thiocyanate bonding, as for example in $[\text{Pd}(\text{diEn})(\text{SCN})]^+$ and $[\text{Pd}(\text{Et}_4\text{diEn})\text{NCS}]^+$, even the small decrease in π -acidity⁴ of the ligand results in a change from N- to S-bonding for thiocyanate ligand.

Recently similar isomerism involving the selenocyanate ion has been reported to depend on non-co-ordinated group⁵. The SeCN^- can co-ordinate to the metals either through nitrogen or selenium or through both. But till now selenocyanate ion was found to co-ordinate through only nitrogen with a single exception of the compound⁶ $[\text{Cu}(\text{MBEn})_2\text{SeCN}]\text{NO}_3$ wherein SeCN^- acts as bridging ligand bonding through both nitrogen and selenium. The cyanate ion (CNO^-), which is usually N-bonded, shows little preference for oxygen end co-ordination.

In this communication, we report the preparation and structure of some thiocyanato, selenocyanato

and cyanato complexes of copper(II) and the effect of distortion from a regular octahedral structure produced by the ligands, propylene diamine and diethylene diamine.

Experimental

Thiocyanato/cyanatobis(propylenediamine)copper(II) :

An ethanolic solution of cupric nitrate was treated with propylenediamine and solid ammonium thiocyanate or potassium cyanate in the stoichiometric ratio 1:2:2. The resulting dark blue solution yielded dark blue crystals on keeping for 10-15 hrs. in air, which were filtered, washed with water, alcohol, ether and then dried in a desiccator for 2-3 days.

Selenocyanatobis(propylenediamine)copper(II)nitrate :

The same method as described above was used to prepare $[\text{Cu}(\text{Pn})_2\text{SeCN}]\text{NO}_3$ with the exception that potassium selenocyanate was used in place of thiocyanate or cyanate.

Thiocyanato/cyanatobis(diethylenediamine)copper(II) :

$\text{Cu}(\text{DiEn})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ was prepared by treating cupric nitrate with diethylenediamine in ethanol. A suspension of $\text{Cu}(\text{DiEn})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in ethanol was treated with solid NH_4SCN or KCNO in the ratio 1:2. The resulting solutions were slowly evaporated in air, which yielded green crystals. They were filtered,

washed with ethanol and ether and dried in a desiccator.

Selenocyanatobis(Diethylenediamine)copper(II)nitrate :

The same method was used as above. The colour of the complex was deep green.

Physical measurements :

Nujol mulls of the solid complexes were placed between rock salt plates and the vibrational spectra of the complexes were recorded using Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer. The electron absorption spectra of solutions were recorded in the range 400-1000 nm with a Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer. The conductivity data in pyridine were obtained using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge, type CLO102 and a dip type cell. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were taken on solid specimens by Guoy method.

Analytical data are presented in Table-1 and spectral data are recorded in Table-2.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes range between 1.84 and 1.91 B.M. indicating the presence of one unpaired electron as expected for a cupric ion. The propylenediamine complexes are highly soluble in pyridine and diethylenediamine complexes are soluble both in pyridine and dimethyl sulfoxide(DMSO). The low molar conductance values of the thiocyanato and cyanato complexes show them to be virtually non-electrolytes. The selenocyanato complexes however indicate higher Λ_M values of 61.0 and 70.4 mhos. (Table-1) suggesting that they are 1:1 electrolytes. This is in agreement with the i.r. spectral data which indicate that nitrate group is ionic and selenocyanate group is bonded to the metal ion.

Infra-red spectra :

Three i.r. active normal modes of vibrations— ν_1, ν_2 and ν_3 are expected⁷ for the nitrate ion (D_{3h} Symmetry). Co-ordination through one or two oxygen atoms lowers the symmetry to C_{2v} , as a result, the i.r. inactive ν_1 vibration becomes active and degeneracy

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, MELTING POINT, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF Cu(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	M.P. (°C)	%Cu		% Anion		Λ_M (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd		
1. [CuPn ₂ SeCN]NO ₃	185d	16.4	16.8	—	—	61.0	1.90
2. [CuPn ₂ (SCN) ₂]	143	19.5	19.4	35.0	35.4	7.7	1.84
3. [CuPn ₂ (NCO) ₂]	160d	21.1	21.4	28.2	28.4	5.7	1.87
4. [Cu(DiEn) ₂ SeCN]NO ₃	250d	15.1	15.6	—	—	70.4	1.89
5. [Cu(DiEn) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	171	17.7	17.9	32.2	32.6	5.9	1.86
6. [Cu(DiEn) ₂ (NCO) ₂]	179	19.2	19.6	25.7	25.9	6.0	1.91

TABLE 2—INFRA-RED AND VISIBLE ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF Cu(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	ν C-N	ν C-S	ν C-O	ν_{max}
1. [CuPn ₂ SeCN]NO ₃	2055 s	—	—	17,980, 12,200
2. [CuPn ₂ (SCN) ₂]	2075 s	710 s	—	17,980
3. [CuPn ₂ (NCO) ₂]	2140 s	—	1305 m	17,090
4. [Cu(DiEn) ₂ SeCN]NO ₃	2050 s	—	—	17,200, 11,760
5. [Cu(DiEn) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	2065 s	720 sh	—	16,660
6. [Cu(DiEn) ₂ (NCO) ₂]	2180 s	—	1353 m	16,980

S-sharp, m-medium, sh-shoulder.

of ν_4 and ν_3 is lifted. Hence altogether six bands are expected for the co-ordinated nitrate ion. Two bands at 1338 and 821 cm^{-1} for $\text{Cu}(\text{Pn})_2(\text{SeCN})\text{NO}_3$ and at 1350 and 818 cm^{-1} for $\text{Cu}(\text{DiEn})_2(\text{SeCN})\text{NO}_3$ were observed in the i.r. spectra which can be assigned to the ν_3 and ν_2 vibrations respectively of an ionic nitrate group. Other band could not be assigned due to overlap of the ligand vibration in that region.

The three vibrational modes of selenocyanate ion, namely $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-Se}}$ and δ_{CNSe} are indicative of the mode of bonding in the complexes. Burmeister⁴ had shown that selenocyanate ion, when bonded through N-, Se- and N, Se- atoms the $\nu_{\text{C-Se}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ frequencies increase and decrease, decrease and increase and decrease in both regions respectively compared to the corresponding frequencies in the free ion. (for KSeCN $\nu_{\text{C-Se}}$ at 558m, $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ at 2069s cm^{-1}). The $\nu_{\text{C-Se}}$ and δ_{NCSe} lie beyond the rock-salt region, hence the present study is limited to only $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ vibration. The bands at 2055 cm^{-1} for $[\text{CuPn}_2(\text{SeCN})]\text{NO}_3$ and at 2050 cm^{-1} for $[\text{Cu}(\text{DiEn})_2\text{SeCN}]\text{NO}_3$ can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ vibration. In the absence of any information regarding $\nu_{\text{C-Se}}$, it is difficult to draw any conclusion regarding the mode of bonding. But, from the ionic nature of the nitrate group and the octahedral nature of the complex as revealed by electronic spectra it is presumed that selenocyanate functions as a bridging group thus imparting hexacoordination to the cupric ion.

The i.r. spectra of $\text{CuPn}_2(\text{SCN})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{DiEn})_2(\text{SCN})_2$ exhibit two bands at 2075 and 710 cm^{-1} and at 2065 and 720 cm^{-1} in the regions of $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ vibrations respectively. Patel and Goldberg⁶ have assigned the bands at 2065, 740 cm^{-1} of $\text{Cu}(\text{MBEn})_2(\text{SCN})_2$ to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ vibrations respectively of S-bonded thiocyanate ligand. It was suggested by Tramer⁸ that on co-ordination, the high frequency $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching) mode is raised by $\sim 30\text{-}40$ cm^{-1} , $\sim 50\text{-}70$ and $70\text{-}120$ cm^{-1} over the $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ band observed at 1963 cm^{-1} for the ionic thiocyanate group indicating terminal N- and S- and bridging thiocyanate group respectively. However, the $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ stretching frequency which drops in S- bonded thiocyanate complexes⁹ relative to that in KSCN , ($\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ at 749 cm^{-1}) can be a more useful guide to the mode of thiocyanate bonding. In the present case, its occurrence at 710 and 720 cm^{-1} clearly indicates the S- bonding. The δ_{NCS} bending could not be recorded due to the limitation of the range of the instrument used. In a similar type of compound, $\text{Cu}(\text{En})_2(\text{SCN})_2$, the S- bonded thiocyanate ligation has been confirmed by X-ray analysis¹.

The cyanato complexes show bands at 2140 and 1305 cm^{-1} and at 2180 and 1353 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ vibrations. It was suggested by Forster and Goodgame¹⁰ that for N- bonded cyanate group, the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ appears at ~ 1300 cm^{-1} and for O- bonded it occurs at a much lower frequency i.e., below 1200 cm^{-1} . Hence the bands at 1305 cm^{-1} and 1353 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ vibration of a N- bonded cyanate group.

Electronic spectra :

All hexa-coordinated copper(II) complexes are tetragonal with D_{4h} or C_{4v} symmetry or rhombic with C_{2v} symmetry. The d^9 configuration is highly susceptible to Jahn Teller distortion and the resulting tetragonal distortion (D_{4h}) leads to further splitting of E_g and T_{2g} levels. The electronic spectra of cupric complexes have been well studied earlier.

The solution spectra of the selenocyanato complexes show a strong band in the range 17,000-18,000 cm^{-1} and a shoulder near $\sim 12,000$ cm^{-1} . The spectra are consistent with the tetragonal symmetry. The main band can be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and the shoulder to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transition. The spectrum of a similar complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{MBEn})_2\text{SeCN}]\text{NO}_3$ shows identical bands, where it is explained that tetragonal structure has been attained via a bridging selenocyanate group.

The thiocyanato and cyanato complexes also reveal bands in the range 16,000-18,000 cm^{-1} which are consistent with tetragonal symmetry.

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